

Creating the International Gemini Observatory's Long-Range Strategic Vision: Looking to the 2030s

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The International Gemini Observatory, operated by NSF's NOIRLab, has begun the process of formulating its [long-range strategy](#) for the next decade. We are looking for broad feedback from both our users and the astronomy community at large in the coming months. This process is a chance to set a path for building the capabilities, priorities, and community of Gemini in the next decade and beyond.

The previous Gemini strategic vision was created in 2016 (approved in 2017), with a view toward operations in 2021 and beyond. The report paid particular attention to synergies with *JWST*, the Rubin Observatory, and future Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) projects. The goal of the strategic vision was to solicit broad community feedback, with all possibilities for the Gemini Observatory considered "on the table."

The final report included the following (paraphrased) recommendations:

1. Leverage Gemini's flexible scheduling model and Gemini South's geographic location to be the premier facility for the follow-up of targets identified by the Vera C. Rubin Observatory's Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST).
2. Remain an observatory predominantly devoted to Principal Investigator (PI)-led science. This is in contrast to having Gemini transition to running large community surveys, for example.
3. Gemini should be the premier hosting facility for ambitious and impactful visitor instruments. We want to particularly engage our partner countries in creating new Gemini instruments to benefit the community as a whole.

We encourage any member of the astronomical community to fill out the 2024 Gemini Strategic Vision Survey. Use this QR code, or the [direct link](#).

Figure 1: Spectral resolution and wavelength coverage for Gemini's current and upcoming instrumentation

4. The future direction of the Gemini telescopes should be allowed to diverge. Given their different geographic locations, overlap with, e.g., LSST, may create an advantage for having specific capabilities in the South versus the North.

These recommendations have helped to facilitate, for example, the development of new instruments like SCORPIO at Gemini South, an eight-channel optical-to-IR imager designed to enable community follow-up of LSST targets. Similarly, because of Maunakea's excellent seeing conditions, the development of multi-conjugate adaptive optics at Gemini North is an example of taking advantage of the capabilities at each site. In light of both LSST and multi-messenger astrophysics, the recommendations emphasized the need for dynamic, real-time scheduling, which will be available through the forthcoming Gemini Program Platform. They emphasized Gemini's commitment to multiple avenues for PI-driven proposals (e.g., Fast

Figure 2: Illustration of Gemini's imaging (left) and IFU (pp) fields of view

Turnaround, Large-and-Long) and Visitor Instrument solicitations.

The new, upcoming formulation of Gemini's strategic vision will require us to plan for the 2030s and anticipate the needs of our community in the next decade. We will begin with a survey for any member of the astronomical community (see QR code), asking for their opinions on Gemini's role in overlapping or complementary science with upcoming facilities, the next big instrumentation projects that the community would like to see Gemini undertake, other areas of potential Gemini infrastructure development (data reduction, scheduling, proposals, etc.), how Gemini can better engage with its user community, and how Gemini can better serve diverse and underrepresented communities — including both astronomers and the general public.

These survey results will be presented to our User's Committee, Science and Technology Advisory Committee, and Board of Directors for integration into the strategic vision. We see this process as a chance not only to evaluate the direction and capabilities of the Gemini Observatory but also to change the direction of current instrumentation and development as needed. Our goal as an observatory is to remain flexible in light of new science and technology. We are committed to enabling the best science from our partners and user community while realizing new opportunities in the coming decades.

Figure 3: Results from the 2016 strategic vision survey indicating respondents who strongly disagree (0) to strongly agree (5) with the following scenarios: a) Gemini South and Gemini North can evolve independently, b) Gemini North and/or Gemini South can move to a partial or full specialization, c) Gemini should maintain at least 50% of the time for PI-driven science, d) Gemini should increase time allocation for very large, very high impact projects that use up to 50% of all telescope time, e) Gemini should enable access to the latest technology through new instrumentation, upgrades to current instrumentation, and a visitor instrumentation program, and f) Gemini should build on current strengths, such as the operational agility of queue observations and the investment in adaptive optics. Histograms for each scenario show their distributions of scores from 0 (left) to 5 (right).